

PHARMACEUTICO-ANALYTICAL STUDY OF JATIPATRADI CHURNA AND ITS MODIFIED FORM OF TOOTHPASTE

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ABSTRACT

The disease *Krimidanta* is described under *Danta roga*. In Ayurvedic classics several treatment modalities with different dosage forms like *Pratisarana*, *Gandoosha* and *Kavala* have been mentioned for the management of *Krimidanta*. Dental caries one of the most common preventable diseases, refers to the localised destruction of susceptible dental hard tissues, it causes symptoms like toothache, tooth sensitivity, abscess, holes in the teeth, and pain while eating or drinking. In the present era, the use of *churna* (herbal powder) for brushing is less preferred due to convenience and patient compliance issues. To address this, *Jatipatradi Churna*, mentioned in *Yogaratanakara* under *Dantaroga Chikitsadhaya* which is having *Krimighna* and *Kandughna* property and traditionally used in the management of *Mukha roga* and *Danta Roga*, has been modified into a toothpaste by using suitable excipients. The Phytochemical and instrumental analysis shows the presence of phenols and phytosterols which has analgesic,

antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties.

KEYWORDS: *Danta roga*, *Jatipatradi churna*, *Jatipatradi toothpaste*.

INTRODUCTION

India has a heritage of traditional herbal medicine. The Ayurvedic system of medicine has described various herbal formulations for disease management. Ayurveda in recent era is attracting global attention due to its holistic approach in the treatment of disease with minimal adverse effects. *Kalpana* is a method of preparation of medicines by using either single drug or a combination of several drugs, the various formulations explained in classics are for the purpose of making the blend compatible and efficient without losing its potency. Any drug to be used as medicine cannot be taken as it is in its raw form, it has to be converted into a new dosage form by which it would be therapeutically fit for use with patient compliance.

Churna being the *Upakalpana* of *Kalka Kalpana* is defined as the dried fine powder of drug obtained after pounding in *Khalwa yantra* (stone mortar) and filtering through cloth.^[1] In Ayurvedic classics, various local therapeutic procedures are described for the effective management of *Mukha roga* and *Danta roga*. These include *Kavala* (gargling), *Gandoosha* (oil holding), *Mukha Dhavana* (mouth rinsing), and *Pratisarana* (application of powders/pastes) based on specific disease conditions. In conditions like bleeding gums and toothache, various herbal *churnas* are mentioned in the classics. example: *Tejohvadi Churna*^[4] used for *Manjana* (brushing the teeth), *Kushtadi Churna*^[5] for *Krimidanta*, *Jatipatradi Churna* in paste form for broader use in *Danta Shoola*, *Dourgandhya*, and *Krimidanta*. *Pratisarana* is mentioned as a key method for conditions like *Krimidanta* (dental caries/infected teeth), *Upakusha* (gingivitis), and other gum/teeth disorders.^[3] The term *Pratisarana kalpana* is similar to *manjan kalpana* available in the *samhitas*, which helps in plague control and maintain the oral health. There are four types of *Pratisarana* like *kalka*, *avaleha*, *madhu* and *churna*. These formulations offer antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and analgesic actions, making them highly effective in both preventive and curative oral care. Oral health is also closely connected to systemic health, as poor dental hygiene can contribute to cardiovascular disease, diabetes, and respiratory infections. Thus, Ayurvedic dentifrices play a preventive role beyond local oral care. *Jatipatradi Churna*, explained in *Yogaratanakara* under *Dantaroga Chikitsadhaya*.^[2] is described to have *Krimighna* (antimicrobial) and *Kandughna* (anti-pruritic) properties. This formulation has been modified into toothpaste form for broader applicability. Toothpaste, a commonly used dentifrice, improves the aesthetic appearance and health of teeth. It promotes oral hygiene by aiding in the removal of dental plaque and food debris from the mouth. Herbal toothpastes are

increasingly popular worldwide due to rising concerns about synthetic chemicals, fluoride toxicity, and consumer preference for natural products. In the present scenario, even if a medicine is effective, lack of attractive packaging and form of dose often reduces consumer acceptance. Therefore, to enhance patient convenience and applicability, a new dosage form of *Jatipatradi Churna*, toothpaste was pharmaceutically prepared, and its analytical profile like Physicochemical, Phytochemical, HPTLC, FTIR, and stability studies provide scientific validation of classical formulations was documented. The development of herbal toothpaste not only preserves the therapeutic efficacy of *Jatipatradi Churna* but also ensures better patient compliance through improved texture, foaming, and packaging.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

- Pharmaceutical study of *Jatipatradi churna* was done in laboratory of Rasashastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana, Government Ayurvedic Medical College, Bangalore, Karnataka and Pharmaceutical preparation of toothpaste was done at Acharya and B. M. Reddy College of Pharmacy, Soladevanahalli, Bengaluru.
- Physicochemical analysis was carried out at Drug testing laboratory, Government central pharmacy, Jayanagar, Ashoka pillar Bangalore.
- Instrumental analysis of FTIR, Viscosity was carried out at the Indian institute of science (IISc), Bengaluru, HPTLC of both samples was carried out at Central Ayurveda Research Institute, Uttarahalli, Kanakpura Main Road, Bengaluru.

PHARMACEUTICAL PREPARATION

Preparation of *Jatipatradi churna*

Jatipatradi churna was prepared by using Pulveriser, *Khalwa yantra*, Sieve of 120#, cotton cloth and weight balance and taking each ingredient is taken separately in *khalwa yantra* till converted into fine powder form and filtered through 120 number mesh. Later all powders are combined together in equal quantity and mixed till homogenous form, the soft, light brown powder with characteristic odour was stored in an airtight container.

Table No 1: Showing Drugs their properties and phytochemical constituents with their activity.^[6,7]

Si.No	Drug	Botanical name	Doshagnata	Action	Phytochemical constituents	Activity
1.	<i>Jatipatra</i>	<i>Jasminum grandiflorum</i>	<i>Tridosha hara</i>	<i>Vranaropaka, Dantarogagna, Vishaghna</i>	Nerolidol, tannins, alkaloid	Anti-microbial, Anti-inflammatory
2.	<i>Punarnava</i>	<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i>	<i>Vata kaphahara</i>	<i>Shothahara</i>	Punarnavine	Analgesics, Anti-inflammatory
3.	<i>Ajamoda</i>	<i>Trachysperum ammi</i>	<i>Kapha Vatahara</i>	<i>Sholahara, Krimighna</i>	Alantolactone, limonene	Anti-bacterial, Anti-inflammatory
4	<i>Kushta</i>	<i>Saussurea lappa</i>	<i>Kapha Vatahara</i>	<i>Raktashodhaka, Varnya,</i>	Thymol, Alkaloids	Analgesic, Anti-bacterial
5.	<i>Vacha</i>	<i>Acorus calamus</i>	<i>Vata Kaphahara</i>	<i>Sholahara, Krimighna</i>	Asarone, Terpenoids	Anti-bacterial, Anti-inflammatory
6.	<i>Haritaki</i>	<i>Terminalia chebula</i>	<i>Tridosha hara</i>	<i>Sholahara, Krimighna</i>	Tannic acid	Anti-bacterial, Antioxidant
7.	<i>Tila</i>	<i>Sesamum indicum</i>	<i>Vatahara</i>	<i>Dantarogagna Vranaropana,</i>	Ascorbic acid, Phytosterols, Phenols	Anti-bacterial, Anti-inflammatory, Analgesic
8.	<i>Badara twak</i>	<i>Ziziphus mauritiana</i>	<i>Vata kaphahara</i>	<i>Raktashodhaka</i>	Quercetin	Analgesic, Anti-bacterial
9.	<i>Gajapippali</i>	<i>Scindapsus officinalis</i>	<i>Kaphavata shamaka</i>	<i>Kantamaya, Jantughna</i>	Proanthocyanidins	Antioxidant, Anti-inflammatory
10.	<i>Shunti</i>	<i>Zingiber officinale</i>	<i>Vata kaphahara</i>	<i>Shophahara,</i>	Gingerol, zingiberene	Analgesics, Anti-inflammatory

Preparation of *Jatipatradi* toothpaste

All the instruments including mortar and pestle, pipettes, measuring cylinders, and packaging materials were disinfected prior to use. To prepare the gel base (Part A), accurately weighed xanthan gum was dispersed in a measured quantity of glycerine in a beaker and left undisturbed for 5 to 10 minutes to allow swelling. For the oil base (Part B), sesame oil, vitamin E, sodium saccharin, and peppermint oil were measured and mixed thoroughly in a separate beaker, then incorporated into the gel base and blended well. In a mortar, a measured quantity of *Jatipatradi churna* and calcium carbonate was mixed properly, after which Part B was gradually added along with measured quantities of surfactants, Geogard ECT

(preservative), and distilled water. The entire mixture was stirred continuously until a smooth, lump-free homogeneous paste was formed. Finally, the volume was adjusted by adding the remaining distilled water, and the prepared toothpaste which was smooth brownish green in colour was packed in disinfected collapsible tubes and sealed tightly to ensure airtight storage.

Table No 2: Ingredients and their quantity used during preparation of *Jatipatradi* toothpaste in trial batches and final batch.

Si. No.	Name of the Ingredients	Trial Batches			Final batch
		JT- 1	JT- 2	JT- 3	
1.	<i>Jatipatradi churna</i> (gm)	3 gm	3.5 gm	1.50 gm	45.8 gm
2.	Calcium carbonate (gm)	3.92 gm	5 gm	3.0 gm	80 gm
3.	Glycerine (ml)	1.54 ml	5 ml	1.50 ml	59.6 ml
4.	Xanthan gum (gm)	0.105 gm	0.2 gm	0.1 gm	7.0 gm
5.	Sesame oil (ml)	0.3 ml	1 ml	0.5 ml	16.9 ml
6.	Vitamin E (ml)	0.1 (ml)	0.1 (ml)	0.1 (ml)	1.9 ml
7.	Saccharine (gm)	0.007 gm	0.05 gm	0.025	0.75 gm
8.	Peppermint oil (ml)	0.1ml	0.1 ml	0.1 ml	4 ml
9.	Cocamidopropyl betadine (ml)	0.03 ml	0.952 ml	0.5 ml	14.5 ml
10.	Sodium lauryl sarcocinate (ml)	0.04 ml	1.176 ml	0.6 ml	16.1 ml
11.	Geogard ect (ml)	0.01 ml	0.01 ml	0.01 ml	1.50 ml
12.	Distilled water (ml)	1.2 ml	4 ml	3.57 ml	51.9 ml

Table No 3: Showing results of Physico-Chemical Analysis of *Jatipatradi churna*

Analytical parameter	<i>Jatipatradi Churna</i>
Loss on drying	7.95%
pH value	5.7
Total ash	8.29%
Acid insoluble ash	3.15%
Water soluble ash	1.18%
Water soluble extractive	21.68%
Alcohol soluble extractive	36.51%
Particle size	97.57% passes through 120 no. mesh

Table No 4: Showing results of Phytochemical Screening of *Jatipatradi* toothpaste.

Phytoconstituents	Result	Grading
ALKALOIDS		
Mayers test	Absent	-
Wagers test	Absent	-
Hagers test	Absent	-
Dragendroffs test	Absent	-
PHYTOSTEROLS	Present	+
PHENOLS (FC reagent method)	Present	++
FLAVONOIDS	Present	-

Table no 5: Showing Parameters of *Jatipatradi* Toothpaste (JT-1, JT-2, JT-3) and final product.

Si no	Physico-chemical	JT-1	JT-2	JT-3	Final product
1	Appearance	Light brown, homogeneous, characteristic odour	Brownish green, homogeneous, characteristic odour	Greenish, homogeneous, characteristic odour	Brownish green, homogeneous, characteristic odour
2	pH	7.4	7.1	7.8	7.1
3	Spreadability (gm.cm/sec)	5.9	6.3	6.1	6.5
4	Tube Extrudability (%)	84.01	84.96	82.12	84.98
5	Viscosity (cp)	1.220×10^5	1.255×10^5	1.186×10^5	1.256×10^5
6	Abrasiveness	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent
7	Moisture content	10%	10%	20%	10%
8	Foaming index	20 ml	40 ml	25 ml	40 ml

HPTLC: Methanolic extracts of *Jatipatradi churna* and Toothpaste were sonicated, filtered (0.45 μ m), and applied on silica gel 60 F₂₅₄ plates using Linomat 5 or ATS 4 applicators. Plates were developed in toluene: ethyl acetate (7:3 v/v), visualized under UV (254/366 nm), derivatized with anisaldehyde-sulphuric acid, and re-examined under white light and 366 nm. Final scanning under absorbance and fluorescence modes provided R_f values, peak data, and chromatograms for comparative fingerprint profiling, this HPTLC finding shows the presence of phytosterols, phenols, terpenoids, alkaloids, tannins which has anti-inflammatory, analgesic and antimicrobial properties in both the samples.

FTIR: The samples were placed on a crystal stand, and this sample were compressed gently by turning the screw of the auto sample pressure, subjected to IR radiations between the range 4000cm⁻¹ to 400cm⁻¹ and the frequency peaks were noted. FTIR finding shows the presence of functional groups like phenols, alkane, alcohol, aromatic esters which has antimicrobial, analgesic, and anti-inflammatory properties.

DISCUSSION

In classical text many dosage form is designed according to disease, patient convenience and form of drug, i.e., indicating the use of whole drug or extraction. Simultaneously Acceptability of society plays a very important role in pharmaceutical industries. There are

four types of *Pratisarana*.^[9] like *kalka*, *avaleha*, *madhu* and *churna* is used in *mukha rogas*, *Pratisarana* is one such form where powder form of drug is applied in buccal cavity, it promotes salivation which helps in plaque control and restores normal contour to the gingiva. In this study without compromising the basic concept, powder form of *Pratisarana* drug is used along with additives of toothpaste, not an extract of drugs. The contents of *Jatipatradi Churna* exhibit antibacterial activity and provide multipurpose care for the teeth, gums, and overall oral hygiene. However, as *Churna* in its powdered form is relatively difficult to handle and use, it has been pharmaceutically modified into a toothpaste for better patient convenience and applicability. During the preparation of the toothpaste, several challenges were encountered, such as excessive thickening of the paste due to the use of excess xanthan gum and low foaming observed in the first and third trial batches, and slight changes in the pH of these trial batches. whereas the 2nd batch showed desirable physical characteristics such as foaming, consistency, texture, and stability, making it the most acceptable formulation. Hence, the final toothpaste was prepared through repeated trial and error methods to achieve homogeneity, foaming index, spreadability, and extrudability. The pH of *Jatipatradi Churna* was 5.7 and toothpaste was 7.1 which is mucosa friendly, is safe for the oral mucosa and helps maintain its integrity, and when the saliva pH drops below the critical threshold of 5.5, the environment becomes acidic, leading to an increased risk of enamel erosion and dental caries. A neutral to slightly alkaline pH is vital for promoting optimal conditions for tooth mineralization and remineralization, particularly for enamel and dentin.^[8] There are not much organoleptic changes were observed between *Jatipatradi churna* and toothpaste except sweet taste in toothpaste due to the presence of saccharine. Phytochemical screening shows the presence of phenols and phytosterols which has antioxidant, antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory and enzyme inhibitory activities which helps in *Krimidanta* (dental caries). HPTLC fingerprint of both the formulations shows the presence of polyphenols and phytosterols and the FTIR finding of both formulation shows the presence of hydroxyl groups, carboxyl groups, alkenes, and ketone functional groups, indicating both samples have anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and antimicrobial properties. *Jatipatradi* Toothpaste, enriched with a blend of herbal actives, has a broad-spectrum absorption across the oral mucosa due to the presence of lipophilic, hydrophilic, and amphiphilic compounds. Lipophilic compounds of *Kushta*, *Gajapippali*, *Vacha*, *Ajamoda* and Peppermint oil rich in volatile oils, terpenoids, and alkaloids are readily absorbed through the lipid-rich mucosal membrane, offering rapid local and mild systemic effects such as anti-inflammatory and analgesic action. Hydrophilic constituents of *Haritaki*, *Punarnava*, and *Shunti*, containing

tannins, flavonoids, and polyphenols, act primarily on the surface, providing antioxidant and antimicrobial benefits with prolonged contact. Amphiphilic agents of Tila contribute both emollient and mild absorption properties, while excipients like Calcium carbonate and Glycerine enhance cleansing, hydration, and retention. Together, these ingredients create a synergistic formulation that supports both therapeutic efficacy and oral hygiene.

An accelerated type of stability study is carried out for 3 months, where the *Jatipatradi* toothpaste was kept in a stability chamber, and the temperature 45⁰C was maintained, the consistency, colour, homogeneity, spreadability, tube extrudability, viscosity, and pH of *Jatipatradi* toothpaste showed no observable changes.

CONCLUSION

An elegant toothpaste formulation was developed using *Jatipatradi Churna*, a classical formulation indicated for *Pratisarana* in *dantarogas*, through multiple trials. The final composition of *Jatipatradi* toothpaste exhibited good aroma, homogeneity, acceptable taste, and met the essential criteria for a modern toothpaste. Accelerated Stability study confirmed the *Jatipatradi* toothpaste will be stable upto 1½ years. This modification not only enhances ease of use and compliance but also retains the therapeutic efficacy of the *Jatipatradi churna*.

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